

Learning English grammar at university: A corpus-based error analysis of Italian B1+ EFL learners

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The acquisition of grammatical competence remains a central concern in EFL contexts, particularly in academic settings where written accuracy constitutes an important marker of language proficiency. Error Analysis provides a valuable theoretical and methodological framework for investigating learner language, as it enables researchers to identify systematic patterns of deviation and explore the cognitive and linguistic processes underlying second-language development. This study examines grammatical errors in the written production of Italian learners of English enrolled in the first year of an undergraduate English-language programme at the University of Naples Federico II (CEFR B1/B1+ level). The analysis is based on a corpus of 244 tests collected during the June–July 2024 testing sessions. Adopting a mixed-methods approach, the study combines quantitative and qualitative analyses to identify recurrent error patterns and investigate their underlying causes. Errors are classified according to their linguistic category and interpreted within the framework of interlanguage theory, with particular attention to the distinction between interlingual and intralingual sources. The findings reveal that reported speech, verb tense and aspect, and question formation turn out to be the most problematic grammatical areas for B1 learners.

Keywords: Cross-Linguistic Influence; English as a Foreign Language; Error Analysis; Foreign Language Acquisition; Interlanguage; Italian Learners

1. Introduction

The development of grammatical competence constitutes a fundamental component of second language acquisition. Although communicative effectiveness encompasses a broad range of linguistic, pragmatic, and sociocultural skills, grammatical accuracy remains an important dimension of language proficiency, particularly in academic writing (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2023, 2026). For learners of English as a Foreign Language (EFL), the acquisition of morphosyntactic structures often represents a significant challenge, as the target

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language may differ substantially from the learner's first language (L1) in terms of grammatical organization and usage (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2020).

The emergence of Error Analysis (EA) as a methodological framework marked a significant shift in the study of learners' language development (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2018). Building upon the seminal work of Corder (1967, 1974), EA challenged earlier behaviourist interpretations that attributed learners' errors primarily to deficiencies in learning or simple interferences from the first language. Instead, EA emphasized the systematic nature of learners' errors and their potential to reveal both developmental processes and cross-linguistic influences. Since its introduction, EA has become a widely employed approach for investigating learner difficulties across diverse linguistic contexts and proficiency levels.

Within EFL research, learners' errors have long been recognised as a valuable source of evidence concerning the processes that underlie language development (cf. Burhansyah et al., 2020; Pichette & Lesniewska, 2018). Errors are not merely by-products of unsuccessful learning; rather, they represent systematic and meaningful evidence of an evolving *interlanguage*, a concept formalised by Selinker (1972), bridging the gap between learners' first language (L1) and the Target Language (TL). Rather than being viewed as random deviations or indicators of failure, errors are increasingly understood as manifestations of an evolving linguistic system that mirrors learners' current stage of interlanguage development. From this perspective, learner language offers important insights into the mechanisms through which foreign language knowledge is constructed, performed, and refined.

Grammatical accuracy remains a persistent challenge for many learners of English. Previous studies have shown that learners frequently encounter difficulties in areas such as tense and aspect, article usage, subject-verb agreement, and prepositional choice (see Caleffi 2023). In the case of Italian EFL learners, these challenges are often associated either with intralingual generalisations or with transfer effects resulting from structural differences between Italian and English morphosyntax.

Against this background, the present study investigates grammatical errors produced by Italian university students enrolled in the first year of an undergraduate English-language programme of transition from B1 to a B1+ level of proficiency. Drawing on a corpus of 244 examination scripts, the study aims to identify the most frequent grammatical error types and to explore their underlying causes through the combined use of quantitative and qualitative methods. Particular attention is devoted to the distinction between 'interlingual' and 'intralingual' sources of error (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2018).

More specifically, the study addresses the following research questions:

- (1) What are the most frequent grammatical errors produced by Italian B1 learners moving to a B1+ level of proficiency?
- (2) Which grammatical domains present the greatest difficulty for Italian B1 learners?
- (3) To what extent can B1 learners' errors be attributed to interlingual or intralingual factors?
- (4) How can Error Analysis contribute to the development of more effective pedagogical interventions in university-level EFL contexts?

By examining authentic learner data from a university setting, this study contributes to ongoing research on learner corpora, interlanguage development, and cross-linguistic influence. In addition, it provides pedagogically relevant insights into the grammatical challenges faced by Italian B1 learners of English and suggests some evidence-based recommendations for grammar instruction in higher education contexts.

2. Background

The study of learner errors has occupied a central position in second language acquisition research for several decades (Chalak & Heidari Tabrizi, 2023; Eckstein et al., 2023). Prior to the emergence of Error Analysis (EA), learner deviations were primarily interpreted through the lens of Contrastive Analysis (CA), which attributed errors to interference from the learner's first language (L1) (Lado, 1957). According to this view, areas of structural difference between the native language and the target language were expected to generate learning difficulties and predictable error patterns. However, empirical research soon revealed important limitations in this approach. Many recurrent deviations appeared to result from developmental processes associated with the acquisition of the target language itself. Therefore, researchers began to focus on the systematic analysis of learner language rather than on predictions derived solely from cross-linguistic comparison.

A major turning point occurred with the publication of Corder's (1967) influential article "The significance of learners' errors". Corder challenged the prevailing perception of errors as evidence of unsuccessful learning and argued instead that they provide valuable insights into the learner's developing linguistic system: "a learner's errors . . . provide evidence of the system of the language that he is using (i.e., has learned) at a particular point in the course" (Corder, 1967, p. 167). From this perspective, learners' errors are not random occurrences, but systematic manifestations of underlying linguistic knowledge. Consequently, they constitute an important source of evidence regarding the processes involved in second-language development.

This reconceptualization laid the foundations for Error Analysis as both a theoretical and methodological framework. Rather than focusing exclusively on what learners fail to produce correctly, EA seeks to explain why specific deviations occur and what they reveal about the learner's evolving competence.

The development of Error Analysis closely intersects with Selinker's (1972) theory of interlanguage. According to Selinker, foreign language learners construct a dynamic linguistic system that is distinct from both the native language and the target language. This intermediate system is continuously modified as learners receive additional linguistic input and refine their hypotheses about the target language. Within this framework, learners' errors acquire a particular theoretical significance. Errors represent observable manifestations of interlanguage development and provide evidence of the strategies learners employ while constructing linguistic knowledge. Errors, therefore, offer valuable insights into both the developmental trajectory of language acquisition and the influence of prior linguistic experience.

Subsequent research further strengthened the connection between Error Analysis and interlanguage theory. Richards (1971, 1994) proposed a distinction between two major sources of learner error: interlingual errors, which arise from transfer from the first language, and intralingual errors, which result from processes internal to second-language development, such as overgeneralisation, simplification, or incomplete rule application. This distinction remains highly influential and continues to inform contemporary analyses of learner language.

In this connection, one of the primary objectives of Error Analysis is to identify the factors that contribute to learner errors. Interlingual errors emerge when learners transfer linguistic features from their native language to the target language. Such transfer may involve lexical, morphological, syntactic, or semantic structures and is particularly common when learners encounter unfamiliar grammatical patterns in the foreign language (cf. Yusuf et al., 2021). Intralingual errors, by contrast, originate within the developing linguistic system itself. These errors reflect learners' attempts to formulate and generalise grammatical rules before they have achieved full mastery of the target language. Common examples include overgeneralisation of syntactic patterns, simplification of complex structures, and incomplete application of grammatical constraints. Unlike interlingual errors, these deviations are not directly attributable to the influence of the native language but reflect developmental characteristics of foreign language acquisition.

Contemporary SLA research generally recognises that learner errors result from the interaction of multiple sources rather than from a single source. Thus, the distinction between interlingual and intralingual influences in relationship with a specific stage of learner proficiency—in our case a transition from B1 to

B1+ level—provides a useful tool for understanding both the linguistic and cognitive dimensions of learner performance.

As for the methodology of Error Analysis, it is typically conducted through a sequence of methodological stages that enable researchers to identify, classify, and interpret learner deviations systematically. Although different models have been proposed, most analyses follow a broadly similar procedure. The first stage involves the collection of learner language data, either written or spoken. The second stage consists in identifying deviations from target-language norms. Researchers then proceed to classify errors according to linguistic category (e.g., morphology, syntax, lexis) and structural characteristics such as omission, addition, misformation, or misordering (Dulay et al., 1982). The following stage focuses on explaining the causes of the identified errors. At this point, researchers examine the extent to which deviations may be attributed to interlingual transfer, developmental processes, or other cognitive and contextual factors. Finally, the pedagogical significance of the errors is evaluated in order to determine which forms represent persistent obstacles to learning and therefore require instructional attention. Through this systematic procedure, Error Analysis serves not only as a descriptive tool but also as a means of investigating the mechanisms underlying second-language development. Its enduring relevance within SLA research lies in its ability to connect learner performance, linguistic theory, and pedagogical practice.

Beyond its theoretical contribution, Error Analysis has significant pedagogical value. By identifying recurring patterns of learner difficulty, EA enables instructors to target problematic grammatical domains more effectively and to design instructional interventions that respond to learners' actual needs rather than to presumed difficulties. In university-level EFL contexts, where grammatical accuracy remains an important component of academic performance, the systematic analysis of learner errors can provide valuable information for curriculum development, materials design, and assessment practices. Moreover, the insights generated through Error Analysis can contribute to a more nuanced understanding of learner development by highlighting the relationship between cross-linguistic influence, instructional input, and interlanguage progression. For these reasons, Error Analysis continues to represent an important methodological approach within both SLA research and language pedagogy, particularly when investigating learner populations whose first language differs substantially from the target language.

3. Method

The study is guided by the assumption that learner errors constitute systematic manifestations of developing linguistic competence and therefore provide valuable evidence regarding the processes involved in foreign language

acquisition at an intermediate level (B1). The study adopts a mixed-methods research design combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to investigate grammatical errors in the written production of Italian EFL learners (Dörnyei, 2007). The integration of quantitative and qualitative analyses allows for a comprehensive examination of learner language, providing both a descriptive overview of error distribution and an interpretative account of the linguistic factors underlying error production (Creswell, 2014; Richards, 2003). The quantitative component focuses on identifying the frequency and distribution of grammatical errors across different types of tasks, thereby revealing the grammatical domains that pose the greatest challenges to learners. The qualitative component complements this analysis by examining the linguistic characteristics of recurrent errors and investigating their potential sources within the framework of Error Analysis and interlanguage theory.

3.1. Participants and context

The participants were undergraduate students enrolled in the first year of the English Language course at the University of Naples Federico II. All participants were native speakers of Italian and were studying English as a foreign language within a university context with the objective to develop B1 skills towards B1+ proficiency. Within the programme, language proficiency is progressively developed across three academic years, corresponding approximately to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) levels B1, B2, and C1 (cf. Ahamat et al., 2024; Mirdehghan Farashah, 2021; Nadal Sanchis & Bello Viruega, 2022). The present study focuses exclusively on first-year students, whose starting level is a B1 level and B1+ is the target proficiency. This learner population was selected because it represents a critical stage of transition from secondary-school language instruction to university-level language study. The analysis is based on test data collected during the June and July 2024 examination sessions, immediately following the completion of the academic year's teaching activities. Because the examinations were administered shortly after the end of class teaching (end of May), data provide a reliable representation of learners' grammatical competence at the conclusion of their first year of language study.

3.2. Data and procedure

The corpus consists of 244 written examination scripts collected during the June–July 2024 testing time. Of these, 148 scripts were obtained from the June session and 96 from the July session. The test focused on grammar and language use and included a range of tasks designed to assess learners' mastery of key grammatical structures. The test format remained consistent

across both sessions, differing only in the specific linguistic items employed. The test included six exercise types:

- (1) Passive constructions;
- (2) Conditional sentences;
- (3) Question formation;
- (4) Reported speech;
- (5) Modal verbs; and
- (6) Verb tense and aspect;

These task types were selected because they target grammatical structures commonly associated with some difficulty among intermediate learners of English, and therefore provide a suitable basis for investigating recurrent error patterns. Across the 244 examination scripts, a total of 2,871 grammatical errors were identified and recorded for analysis.

The analysis followed the procedures commonly associated with Error Analysis research (Corder, 1967; Ellis, 1985; James, 1998). The first stage involved the systematic identification of grammatical deviations from standard English norms. Only grammatical errors were included in the analysis. Pragmatic misunderstanding was excluded from the investigation due to the nature of the tasks. Once identified, errors were classified according to two complementary analytical frameworks. First, errors were categorised according to their linguistic domain, including:

- article usage;
- subject-verb agreement;
- verb tense and aspect;
- prepositional usage;
- reported speech;
- question formation;
- modal constructions; and
- passive constructions.

Second, errors were interpreted according to their presumed sources. Following Richards (1971, 1994), a distinction was made between (1) interlingual errors, resulting from transfer from Italian; and (2) intralingual errors, arising from developmental processes within the learners' interlanguage system. This dual classification framework enabled both quantitative measurement and qualitative interpretation of learner difficulties.

Raw error frequencies were calculated for each exercise type. This procedure provided an overview of the distribution of errors across the examination and allowed the identification of grammatical domains associated with the largest

number of learner deviations. The analysis, therefore, was based on one single indicator—i.e., Error Frequency, or the total number of errors recorded in a given exercise. This measure provided a meaningful representation of B1 learners' performance. Nevertheless, the qualitative analysis focused on the most recurrent grammatical error categories identified through the quantitative phase. Representative learner examples were selected from the corpus and analysed in relation to both interlanguage theory and cross-linguistic influence. The objective was not merely to describe error forms but also to explore the linguistic mechanisms that may have contributed to their production. Special attention was given to the role of Italian *vis à vis* English structural differences, particularly in areas involving auxiliary selection, tense–aspect distinctions, and prepositional collocations. This interpretative approach enabled a deeper understanding of the relationship between learner performance and underlying grammatical knowledge.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the corpus is restricted to a single institutional context and therefore may not be representative of all Italian learners of English at the B1 level. Second, the analysis is based exclusively on written examination data and does not include spoken production. Nevertheless, the relatively large corpus and the combination of quantitative and qualitative procedures provide a robust basis for examining recurrent patterns of grammatical difficulty among Italian university learners of English.

4. Results

A total of 2,871 grammatical errors were identified across the 244 examination scripts included in the corpus. To obtain a comprehensive understanding of learner performance, the analysis considered error frequency as providing information about the overall distribution of errors across grammatical categories. The results reveal substantial variation across grammatical domains, suggesting that some structures pose significantly greater challenges than others for intermediate Italian EFL learners.

4.1. Quantitative analysis: Error frequency

The distribution of errors across task types indicates that learners encountered the greatest difficulty in the management of time categories (tenses and aspect), as can be seen in Table 1 (below). The conditional sentence exercise produced the lowest number of errors, with 189 instances corresponding to 6.6% of the total error count. Aspect/tense variations and reported speech were the tests producing the highest number of errors. The findings in the table suggest that grammatical accuracy decreases when learners are required to

generate linguistic forms independently rather than recognise them from a limited set of alternatives.

Table 1
Percentage of Errors in Each Type of Exercise

Exercises	%
Formulating conditional sentences (1 st , 2 nd and 3 rd degree)	6.6
Modal verbs usage (open cloze test)	7.7
Active>Passive sentence transformation (usage of auxiliaries)	8.5
Question formation (from given answers)	11.3
Reported speech (transformation from direct speech)	11.7
Aspect/tense variations: perfective, imperfective, duration forms (open cloze test)	15.5
Other errors (lexis, missing answers)	38.7

4.2. Qualitative analysis of recurrent error types

To complement the quantitative findings, a qualitative analysis was conducted on the most recurrent error categories. Particular attention was devoted to structures that displayed high frequency and density scores, as these represent persistent areas of learner difficulty.

4.2.1. Verb tense and aspect

One of the most prominent sources of difficulty concerned the English tense–aspect system. Learners frequently produced errors involving auxiliary selection, tense sequencing, and distinctions among simple, progressive, and perfect constructions. The findings support previous research (Caleffi, 2023; Collins, 2007) indicating that tense and aspect constitute persistent challenges for Italian EFL learners. Examples (1) and (2) demonstrate recurring difficulties in the use of the present perfect progressive and past perfect forms.

- (1) Error: * Ever since the crash, I am not been able to sleep well.
correct: I have not been able to sleep well.
- (2) Error: * Dad is cooking this meal for hours.
correct: Dad has been cooking this meal for hours.

At B1 level, errors in managing duration forms (e.g., for/since, present perfect vs past simple, progressive aspect with duration) can often be classified as intralingual errors due to overgeneralization, especially in the sense described in classic error analysis (Richards, 1971, 1994). However, these errors appear to be closely related to structural differences between Italian and English. Unlike English, which grammaticalizes aspect through distinct verbal forms, Italian often relies on contextual interpretation or multifunctional compound tenses. Italian EFL learners may transfer Italian time patterns into English,

resulting in inaccurate tense-aspect selection. Therefore, at B1 level, errors in expressing duration (e.g., misuse of present perfect and prepositions such as *for/since*) can often be explained as intralingual errors, particularly due to overgeneralisation and simplification of emerging tense-aspect rules, though L1 transfer may also contribute.

4.2.2. Reported speech

Reported speech emerged as one of the most problematic grammatical domains according to the error-frequency analysis. Most errors involved failures to apply tense back-shifting appropriately. Typical examples include (3) and (4):

- (1) Error: * Mark asked me whether my friends arrived yesterday.
correct: Mark asked whether my friends had arrived the day before.
- (2) Error: * The police officer asked where he was yesterday.
correct: The police officer asked where he had been the day before.

In both cases, learners failed to modify the tense structure required in English reported speech. As we noticed before, the explanation can be classified as an intralingual error due to a tendency to overgeneralise simple past forms against more refined tense/aspect constructions dealing with the past (past continuous, past perfect, past perfect continuous). However, this pattern is also consistent with cross-linguistic influence from Italian. In many contexts, Italian allows the retention of tense forms in reported speech, whereas English requires systematic backshifting. As a result, learners may transfer L1 conventions into their English production, generating recurrent errors in tense sequencing. The high frequency of these errors suggests that reported speech remains insufficiently automatized even among B1 EFL learners who have received explicit instruction on the structure. In this case, the intralingual and the interlingual error sources are mixed and contribute to outline a B1 learner profile whose development is characterized in a way that is specific in comparison to elementary learners' profiles (dominance of interlingual error sources) or advanced learners' profiles (dominance of intralingual error sources).

4.2.3. Question formation

Another area of significant difficulty concerned question formation. Learners frequently produced errors involving auxiliary placement and word order. These deviations often reflected direct transfer from Italian sentence structure, particularly in contexts where English requires obligatory subject-auxiliary inversion. The findings demonstrate that syntactic reorganisation represents a major challenge during the intermediate stages of EFL development. Because

question formation requires simultaneous control of word order, auxiliary selection, and tense marking, B1 learners may struggle to coordinate multiple grammatical operations within a single utterance.

4.4. Interlingual and Intralingual Influences

A central objective of this study was to investigate the sources of learner errors. The qualitative analysis indicates that a substantial proportion of high-frequency errors made by B1 EFL learners can be attributed to a combination between intralingual and interlingual error sources. Both transfer effects (interlingual) and grammatical generalisation (intralingual) were particularly evident in the domains of (a) tense and aspect, (b) reported speech, and (c) question formation. In each of these areas, learners frequently produced forms that mirrored Italian grammatical structures rather than English target-language norms. Likewise, these error categories may be interpreted as intralingual phenomena resulting from overgeneralisation or incomplete rule acquisition, suggesting the complexity of grammatical competence at an intermediate level of language proficiency. These findings provide further support for interlanguage theory by demonstrating that learner language emerges through the interaction of developmental processes and L1-based transfer strategies.

5. Discussion

The findings reveal that grammatical difficulty is not distributed evenly across linguistic domains. Structures requiring learners to manipulate tense, aspect, auxiliary systems, or syntactic transformations generated substantially higher error rates than structures involving more predictable grammatical patterns. Particularly noteworthy is the prominence of reported speech as one of the most difficult grammatical categories. Although this structure is frequently taught in EFL curricula, learners continue to experience difficulties in applying tense-sequencing rules accurately. This finding suggests that explicit instruction alone may be insufficient to ensure procedural mastery. More broadly, the results underscore the continuing influence of learners' first language on grammatical performance. The prevalence of transfer-related errors supports previous research emphasising the role of cross-linguistic influence in second-language development and highlights the importance of addressing structural mismatches between Italian and English through targeted instructional practices. Overall, the data suggest that grammatical competence at the intermediate level is shaped by the interaction of developmental factors based on intralingual generalisations and language-transfer processes, thus reinforcing key assumptions of both Error Analysis and interlanguage theory.

6. Conclusion

The present study investigated grammatical errors in the written production of Italian B1 learners of English through a combined quantitative and qualitative analysis. The findings reveal that grammatical difficulties are not distributed uniformly across linguistic domains. Rather, learners exhibit persistent challenges in a limited number of areas, most notably verb tense and aspect, reported speech, and question formation.

The quantitative analysis demonstrated that verb tense and aspect produced the highest error frequency, indicating that this structure represents one of the most problematic grammatical domains in the corpus. Reported speech, together with question formation, also generated consistently high error rates. These findings suggest that learners experience difficulty when grammatical accuracy depends on the coordination of multiple linguistic components, including (a) tense selection, (b) auxiliary use, (c) syntactic transformations, and (d) word order.

The qualitative analysis provides further insight into the nature of these difficulties. Across the most frequent error categories, a substantial proportion of B1 learner deviations appear to be associated both with intralingual generalisations and with transfer processes from Italian. This pattern is particularly evident in the domains of reported speech and tense-aspect morphology, where English and Italian differ considerably in the grammatical expression of temporal relations. The strategies adopted by B1 learners to solve grammatical impasse can rely on L1 structures or the extension of foreign language structures that are already mastered.

These findings are consistent with previous research on interlanguage development and cross-linguistic influence (Odlin, 1989; Gass & Selinker, 2008). The results support the view that learner language is shaped not only by developmental processes internal to foreign language acquisition, but also by the continued influence of previously acquired linguistic knowledge. The interaction between these factors contributes to the emergence of systematic error patterns (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2018) that characterise the intermediate stages of language development.

From a pedagogical perspective, the results suggest several implications for grammar instruction addressed to B1 EFL learners in university-level contexts. Firstly, grammar instruction should move beyond isolated rule presentation and encourage learners to develop a deeper understanding of how grammatical structures function within authentic communicative contexts. Exposure to meaningful language input may be particularly beneficial in areas such as tense/aspect variations or reported speech, where rule-based explanations alone are often insufficient. Secondly, the findings highlight the value of Error

Analysis as a diagnostic tool for language teaching. By systematically identifying recurrent learner difficulties, instructors can adapt classroom activities, assessment practices, and remedial interventions to address specific areas of need. Rather than treating errors merely as indicators of failure, teachers can use them as evidence of learners' developing linguistic systems and as a source of information for pedagogical decision-making. Finally, the results underscore the importance of adopting a developmental perspective on learner language, and this move seems to be crucial when dealing with B1/intermediate EFL learners. Many of the identified errors should not be viewed solely as deficiencies requiring correction, but as manifestations of an evolving interlanguage system. Understanding the variable sources and patterns of these errors may enable teachers to design more effective instructional strategies that support learners as they progress toward higher levels of proficiency.

Authors' Statement

The authors discussed and conceived the article together. In particular, Paolo Donadio is responsible for §1, §2, §3; Ajernisa Xhemali for §3.1, §3.2, §4, §5, §6.

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